

Methods for Earth-Based Falsework in Multi-Material Additive Manufacturing at an Architectural Scale

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Abstract. This study delves into the promising potential of multi-material Additive Manufacturing (AM) for large-scale architectural applications. It specifically focuses on the innovative integration of dissolvable and reusable, single-sided falsework within 3D-printed structures. Unlike traditional dual-sided moulds that limit design capabilities and increase labour, this method effectively utilises earth-based falsework that not only can be reused for subsequent prints but also significantly contributes to minimising waste and reducing overall material requirements. Through this lens, the research tackles the inherent challenges in creating complex, non-self-supporting forms, while also underscoring effective strategies aimed at optimising the deposition of structural materials both alongside and on top of the falsework. In its detailed analysis, the study examines various factors such as nozzle angles, different printing directions, and the implementation of dynamic adjustments. Ultimately, this research demonstrates how multi-material Additive Manufacturing can adeptly overcome the inherent limitations presented by mono-material approaches, thereby offering enhanced design flexibility, sustainability, and operational efficiency. This paves the way for innovative advancements in architectural design and construction practices, showcasing the future potential of AM in creating sustainable and adaptive structures.

Keywords. Multi-material Additive Manufacturing, Building technology, 3D printable concrete, Digital Falsework, Mechanical behaviour.

1. Introduction

Traditional construction methods like moulding, casting, and scaffolding are often inefficient and costly, with formwork expenses accounting for 35-60% of construction costs (McKinsey & Company, 2017; Scheder-Bieschin et al., 2024). Scaffolding labour can represent up to 45% of direct field labour expenses, and conventional formworks generate significant waste, particularly single-use wooden and limited-use metal systems (Curth et al., 2024; Yin & Caldas, 2022).

Additive Manufacturing (AM), especially large-scale 3D printing, offers a transformative alternative by enabling complex, custom forms with reduced labour costs and material waste (Van Woensel et al., 2018). However, mono-material printing limits design flexibility, a challenge addressable through multi-material approaches utilising different materials for structure and falsework (Hou et al., 2021).

While sacrificial or dissolvable support materials are established in polymer-based AM technologies (Herzberger et al., 2019), large-scale construction AM introduces complex challenges. Printing structural materials alongside earth-based falsework requires precise material deposition, particularly for shapes with varying angles and curved surfaces. Critical considerations include maintaining continuous material flow, preventing falsework damage, and ensuring accurate extruder performance.

This research explores multi-material printing techniques for earth-based falsework and cement-based structures, optimizing deposition strategies for complex forms and focusing on sustainable, reusable materials.

2. Background

2.1. RELEVANT WORK

Concrete 3D printing has primarily focused on mono-material approaches, while polymer-based Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies like Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) have successfully explored dual-material printing systems (Herzberger et al., 2019; Hou et al., 2021). Polymer printing techniques enable the simultaneous deposition of structural and support materials through precise extruder control, creating complex shapes by alternating material extrusion (Redwood et al., 2017; Tay et al., 2019).

However, these principles cannot be directly applied to cementitious printing. Unlike polymers, cementitious materials prefer a continuous flow to prevent premature hardening within the pipes or nozzle (Bentur et al., 2023b). Pausing material flow risks block the extruder system, necessitating innovative approaches for constructing multi-material AM.

Few studies have explored limited strategies to expand mono-material printing capabilities, such as using 3D-printed moulds as formwork and adjusting printing parameters to create complex overhanging structures (Cuevas et al., 2021; Curth et al., 2024; Mozaffari et al., 2024). Despite these advances, developing an approach that uses one material as temporary falsework for another—supporting construction and then dissolving or integrating into the final structure—remains a critical area for exploration.

Multi-material AM printing presents a promising solution by leveraging material synergies to enhance structural performance. Our study addresses this gap by proposing a novel approach involving dissolvable or reusable falsework systems. By implementing sequential printing—starting with an earth-based support system and subsequently applying cement—we aim to minimise extruder interference and enable non-planar printing (Battaglia et al., 2019).

This method aligns with sustainable construction goals by reducing waste, facilitating on-site material recycling, and exploring new architectural possibilities through innovative material application.

2.2. CHALLENGES IN DIGITAL FALSEWORK

Integrating digital falsework into large-scale AM involves overcoming several challenges:

- **Material Compatibility**—Falsework must maintain stability during printing while remaining removable and reusable post-construction. Ensuring seamless interaction between cement elements and earth-based falsework is crucial for mechanical and structural performance.
- **Continuous Deposition**—Cementitious materials require an uninterrupted flow to prevent premature hardening within the delivery system, which can lead to blockages and equipment failure (Asaf et al., 2023). Unlike polymer-based AM systems, where extrusion can be paused and resumed, cementitious AM requires continuous deposition to maintain material consistency and avoid disruptions.
- **Printing Sequence**—This research employs a sequential printing strategy: the falsework is printed first, followed by the structural materials. Ensuring the nozzle does not interfere with or damage the falsework during printing requires careful calibration, particularly when printing on sloped surfaces.
- **Geometric Complexity**—Architectural forms, such as double-curved surfaces and irregular profiles, pose challenges for material deposition. High-quality results require advanced path planning, adaptive nozzle positioning, and precise layer height control. Robotic arm movements need careful calibration to navigate these geometries. Printing at angles introduces complex trajectories that challenge the arm's capabilities. Establishing guidelines for robotic movements is crucial for accurate material deposition. Non-planar printing techniques enable innovative designs but require careful calibration and planning to avoid structure interference.

Figure 1. Extrusion profile showing material deposition at 90° and 70° nozzle angles, illustrating the impact of nozzle orientation on layer stability and adhesion.

- **Nozzle Angle and Distance**—The nozzle angle and distance greatly affect deposition quality, with cone-shaped nozzles needing optimisation for flowability and extruder size. A 90° nozzle angle results in elliptical profiles but must be close to the surface, increasing damage risk to the falsework. Conversely, a 70° angle offers the best balance for complex shapes, maintaining a distance of 1.5 times the layer width to reduce damage. This angled method, however, creates asymmetrical trapezoid profiles with increased pressure on the far zone of the falsework. Proper spacing between the structure and falsework is crucial; being too close can deform the falsework, while being too far leads to poor layer adhesion and potential collapse, as shown in Figure 1.

3. Method and setup

3.1. METHOD

This paper presents an approach to multi-material additive manufacturing, integrating earth-based falsework with cement printing. The process involves (a) Design: Enhancing models for material efficiency and compatibility with multi-material printing. (b) Printing Falsework: Building a robust earth-based structure for temporary support. (c) Printing Structure: Precisely depositing cement onto the falsework. (d) Falsework Removal: Cleaning the falsework for future use. (e) Reusing: Recycling the cleaned material to enhance future designs. This approach minimizes waste by reusing falsework and removes the need for double-sided moulds, thus improving the production of intricate architectural designs, as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research method workflow

The experiments evaluated the limitations and capabilities of printing structural materials with digital falsework. By focusing on walls and geometric profiles, the tests examined how different nozzle angles influenced deposition quality. The findings aim to inform future design and printing processes for complex architectural shapes. The objectives of the experimental framework were as follows: (i) Understanding the effects of nozzle angles and dynamic adjustments: Investigate how varying nozzle angles and dynamic adjustments affect material deposition quality, adherence, and layer consistency across different surface geometries. These include falsework prisms with base angles of 30°, 45°, and 60°, as well as double-curved domes. (ii) Evaluating the nozzle distance from the falsework: Assess the impact of nozzle positioning on deformation, material stability, and adherence, ensuring that the falsework remains undamaged during the deposition process. (iii) Exploring planar and non-planar printing methods: Examine the effectiveness of planar and non-planar techniques on diverse geometric configurations, including sloped and freeform surfaces, to establish best practices for structural material deposition.

3.2. SETUP AND MATERIALS

An earth-based mixture was used as falsework, based on a mixture developed by Asaf et al. (Asaf et al., 2023), consisting of sand, water, and local kaolinite clay. The structural cementitious mix followed Asaf et al. (Asaf et al., 2024) guidelines and included CEMI 52.5R White Cement, siliceous sand, and polycarboxylate admixtures.

A KUKA KR50R2100 robotic arm with a 10 mm nozzle was used for precise deposition. Earth-based mixtures were extruded using a MAI®2PUMP-LYRA, while a MAI® MULTIMIX-3D mortar pump delivered cementitious materials (Figure 3) Toolpaths were designed in Rhinoceros 8 and controlled using Grasshopper® plugins and the KUKA | PRC module.

The falsework was printed first, with a layer height of 10 mm, a layer width of 17 mm, and a uniform infill density using concentric or contour patterns. A wall thickness of four layers was maintained for stability. Printing velocities were set at 150 mm/s, with fixed nozzle angles of 90° for initial testing. Subsequently, the cementitious material was printed directly on top of and alongside the falsework, testing nozzle angles of 90°, 80°, and 70° to assess their influence on layer consistency, adherence, and structural stability (Printing process diagram Figure 4).

Figure 3. Robotic AM printing setup (Technion Centre for Advanced Construction, TACC, 2024).

The earth-based falsework is intended for several usage cycles. It is methodically detached through water spraying or mechanical means. After recovery, the material is screened to eliminate any cement remnants and is blended with extra water and clay as necessary to attain the best printing consistency.

Figure 4. Printing process left to right: (1) Soil Falsework Printing: Printing the temporary support. (2) Structural Printing: Printing the main structure from bottom to top at a 70° angle. (3) Final Structure: Post falsework removal. (4) Free printed structure.

4. Results and Discussion

Effect of nozzle angle and distance on print quality—The nozzle angles were assessed to determine the best degree for printing structures. A 70° nozzle angle proved optimal for complex designs as it minimised falsework damage and ensured consistent material deposition at 1.5 times the layer width, effectively balancing adherence and structural integrity. In contrast, a 90° angle required maintenance of a layer-width distance to prevent damage, while the 80° angle, which initially worked well at 1.3 times the layer width, had to be adjusted to 1.5 times to correct inconsistencies. 90° Nozzle Angle: This angle allowed even deposition on flat surfaces but struggled with sloped shapes. The 70° and 80° angles performed exceptionally well on inclined and irregular surfaces, with the 70° angle showing the greatest adaptability.

Effect of nozzle direction on print quality—The nozzle's alignment with the print direction is essential. Printing from bottom to top on inclined surfaces reduces falsework interference, facilitates better material adherence, and lowers the risk of nozzle obstruction (Figure 7). Conversely, printing from top to bottom results in uneven layers, deformation due to extrusion pressure, and compromised stability. Modifying the printing angle to the opposite can improve deposition quality, underscoring the need for adaptable strategies, although this method may pose a risk of falsework damage in certain cases (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Non-Planar Printing at 70° Nozzle: Comparing Bottom-to-Top and Top-Down Behaviors. Bottom-to-top printing demonstrates consistent results, while top-down printing prefers an opposing nozzle angle, risking falsework.

Effect of dynamic nozzle adjustments on print quality—By synchronising dynamic nozzle adjustments with surface curvature, we achieved consistent material deposition across intricate shapes. Nonetheless, this method encountered difficulties preserving uniform layer thickness, particularly when dealing with notable curvature variations. Our research indicates that advancements in real-time flow control systems might improve performance in these situations.

Figure 6. Comparison of Planar vs Non-Planar Printing: Top-to-Bottom Consistency in Planar, Material Deposition Challenges for Non-Planar.

Planar vs. Non-Planar Printing— Both planar and non-planar printing methods have been effective; however, planar printing stands out due to its bottom-to-top technique. This approach facilitates optimal nozzle orientation, producing cleaner and more precise material deposition. In contrast, non-planar printing involves descending from top to bottom after reaching the highest point, which presents several challenges. Notably, continuous extrusion during the downward motion leads to material accumulation and an uncontrolled mess around the print. This situation emphasises the necessity for solutions like dynamically adjusting the nozzle angle or temporarily halting extrusion to preserve the print quality. Although non-planar printing can create intricate shapes, these challenges highlight the crucial need for improved extrusion control in future endeavours (Figure 6).

5. Conclusions

This research highlights the potential and challenges of integrating digital falsework in large-scale additive manufacturing. Evaluating materials, nozzle configurations, and printing strategies yielded key insights:

Planar vs. Non-Planar Printing: Planar printing proved more reliable due to its bottom-to-top approach, which enhances deposition control and reduces falsework interference. While non-planar printing is effective for complex forms, it struggles with material buildup during downward movements, emphasising the need for better extrusion control, including dynamic nozzle adjustments or temporary pauses.

Nozzle Configuration and Distance: A 70° nozzle angle is optimal for complex shapes, balancing deposition quality and protecting falsework. A nozzle-to-falsework

distance of 1.5 times the layer width is essential to prevent deformation and ensure adhesion stability.

Falsework Design and Material Compatibility: Earth-based falsework offers a stable support system that is compatible with cementitious materials for multi-material AM. Printing falsework first and structural materials later is effective, particularly for sloped and irregular forms.

Future Directions: To improve deposition accuracy and quality, advancements in dynamic nozzle adjustment, synchronised pump control, and refined robotic path planning are needed. Addressing these challenges will enhance the production of complex architectural forms. This research successfully tested single-sided falsework up to 50 cm in height. Future studies should focus on exploring taller structures and evaluating their stability and performance under various conditions. Additionally, further testing on strength and structural behaviour is necessary to ensure the scalability and robustness of this method for larger and more demanding architectural applications.

This study sets a framework for utilising digital falsework in AM to expand design possibilities, reduce waste, and enhance construction efficiency, offering valuable insights for advancing multi-material AM in architecture and construction (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Bottom-to-Top Printing Setup

Figure 8. Single-Sided Falsework – Easy Removal and Prepared for Reuse

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